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ЁШЛАР ТАФАККУРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА СУНЪИЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ ВА НАНОТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИНГ ЎРНИ.....78

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**ENSURING GENDER BALANCE IN THE EDUCATION AND SCIENCE SYSTEM:
THE STRATEGIC ROLE OF WOMEN'S PARTICIPATION AND THE EXPERIENCE OF
UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract: This article examines the issue of ensuring gender equality in the education system based on the recommendations of international organizations and the experience of Uzbekistan. The gender composition of teaching staff, preschool education coverage, and women's participation in higher education and scientific activities are analyzed using statistical data. In addition, the effectiveness of state policies and practical programs aimed at supporting women scholars is assessed.

Keywords: gender equality, education policy, teaching staff, women scholars, education statistics.

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**ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ ГЕНДЕРНОГО БАЛАНСА В СИСТЕМЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И
НАУКИ: СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКАЯ РОЛЬ УЧАСТИЯ ЖЕНЩИН И ОПЫТ
УЗБЕКИСТАНА**

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается вопрос обеспечения гендерного равенства в системе образования на основе рекомендаций международных организаций и опыта Узбекистана. На основе статистических данных анализируются гендерный состав педагогических кадров, охват дошкольным образованием, а также участие женщин в системе высшего образования и научной деятельности. Кроме того, оценивается эффективность государственной политики и практических программ, направленных на поддержку женщин-учёных.

Ключевые слова: гендерное равенство, образовательная политика, педагогические кадры, женщины-учёные, образовательная статистика.

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ТАЪЛИМ ВА ИЛМ-ФАН ТИЗИМИДА ГЕНДЕР МУВОЗАНАТИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШ: АЁЛЛАР ИШТИРОКИНИНГ СТРАТЕГИК ЎРНИ ВА ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ТАЖРИБАСИ

Аннотация: Мазкур мақолада таълим тизимида гендер тенглигини таъминлаш масаласи халқаро ташкилотлар тавсиялари ва Ўзбекистон тажрибаси асосида таҳлил қилинган. Статистик маълумотлар асосида педагогик кадрлар гендер таркиби, мактабгача таълим камрови ҳамда аёлларнинг олий таълим ва илмий фаолиятдаги иштироки ўрганилган. Шунингдек, аёл олимларни қўллаб-қувватлашга қаратилган давлат сиёсати ва амалий дастурлар самарадорлиги баҳоланган.

Калит сўзлар: гендер тенглиги, таълим сиёсати, педагогик кадрлар, аёл олимлар, таълим статистикаси.

Introduction. In modern society, the education system is considered an important institution for social justice and sustainable development. Ensuring gender equality within this system is not only a matter of protecting human rights but also a key factor in improving the quality and effectiveness of education. Approaches developed by international organizations require the creation of equal opportunities for girls and boys, women and men at all stages of education.

In Uzbekistan, special attention is also paid to gender issues in education and science. The gender composition of teaching staff, the activity of women scholars, and the state support mechanisms implemented by the government serve as important indicators of ongoing reforms in this field. Therefore, this study aims to comprehensively analyze the current state of gender equality in the education system.

Literature Review: Existing literature emphasizes that gender equality has a direct impact on the quality of education. National publications highlight women's active participation in the education system and their social status [1; 2].

Official data and government information sources provide evidence of programs, grants, and competitions aimed at supporting women scholars [3]. Moreover, scientific forums organized to strengthen regional cooperation contribute to the integration and collaboration of women researchers [4].

Statistical collections offer precise numerical data on the gender composition of educational institutions, preschool enrollment, and the share of women in science [5]. These sources constitute the empirical basis of the study.

Methodology. The following research methods were employed in the course of the study:

- analysis of statistical data;
- comparative method (comparison of international and national indicators);
- content analysis of documents and official sources;
- descriptive and analytical approaches.

The data were mainly collected from state statistical reports, recommendations of international organizations, and mass media sources [1–5].

Analysis and Results. At the international level, ensuring gender equality in the education system is recognized as an essential condition for sustainable social development. Reputable international organizations such as UNESCO and UNICEF identify gender equality as one of the key indicators in the analysis of educational statistics and recommend systematic monitoring of the gender composition of pupils and students at all stages of education—primary, secondary, and higher levels. This approach helps to identify existing disparities in access to educational opportunities and to eliminate them in a timely manner [5, p. 26].

The International Labour Organization emphasizes the need to introduce specific labor policies aimed at ensuring gender equality among teaching staff. In this regard, equal wages, decent working conditions, professional development, and equal opportunities for career advancement for both women and men are considered fundamental criteria. In addition, the United Nations recommends analyzing recruitment processes, appointments to managerial positions, and career progression in educational institutions based on gender composition [5, p. 27].

National statistical data reveal certain characteristics in the gender distribution of pedagogical staff. In particular, women dominate in general secondary education institutions, accounting for 69.9 percent of the total teaching staff. In specialized secondary and professional education institutions, the share of women is 57.6 percent and 57.2 percent respectively. Only in higher education institutions does the number of male teachers exceed that of women by 9.2 percent. This situation indicates that gender composition varies across different stages of the education system and highlights the need to ensure balance in personnel policy [5, p. 28].

Preschool enrollment is also an important indicator in assessing the quality of education. According to UNESCO Institute for Statistics data, 60.9 percent of preschool-age children worldwide were enrolled in educational institutions in 2020, while this figure was 44.0 percent in Uzbekistan. This difference can be explained by national socio-cultural factors. In many Uzbek families, traditional home-based childcare practices remain common, with mothers and elder family members—grandparents—actively involved in upbringing. Therefore, although institutional coverage is relatively low, children still have opportunities for socialization and development within the family environment [5, p. 29].

At the same time, ensuring gender balance among teaching staff, especially in extracurricular education institutions, plays a crucial role in improving education quality and creating an inclusive and balanced learning environment. In particular, equal participation of girls and boys in information and communication technologies and digital skills education is considered a strategic priority. This not only enhances educational effectiveness but also contributes to preparing competitive human resources for the digital economy [5, p. 30].

A gradual reduction in gender disparities is also observed in scientific activities. According to international statistics, the share of women among academic and research staff in higher education institutions increased from 31.5 percent in 1975 to 39.1 percent in 2000 and reached 43.1 percent by 2022. This figure is particularly high in post-Soviet countries, where women scholars account for more than 60 percent in Russia, Kazakhstan, and Belarus. This demonstrates that women's active participation in education and science has become a strong institutional tradition [5, pp. 31–32].

The experience of Uzbekistan also confirms this trend. For example, in 1997, women constituted 80 percent of the employees at the Education Center of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1], indicating their leading role in the development of textbooks, methodological manuals, and educational materials. Moreover, the activities of individual women educators and scholars—such as the creation of the “Savod” textbook based on the new Uzbek Latin alphabet—demonstrate their significant contribution to improving educational content [2].

In recent years, systematic measures have been implemented within the framework of state policy to support women's scientific activity. Within the “Women Scholars” research project competition, hundreds of research initiatives have been funded, resulting in important scientific achievements in chemistry, physics-mathematics, biology, and agriculture [3]. In addition, international platforms such as the “SheScience” forum contribute to strengthening cooperation among women scholars in the region and promoting joint research projects [4].

Conclusion. In conclusion, ensuring gender equality in the education and science system is not only an expression of social justice but also a key factor in improving educational quality and fostering innovative development. Providing equal opportunities for women and men and enabling them to fully realize their professional and scientific potential directly contributes to the intellectual and economic development of the country.

References:

1. Tuymanova, Kh. *Nazokat saltanati* [The Realm of Grace] // Ma'rifat newspaper. – Tashkent, 8 March 1997.
2. Obiddinov, A. *Orzulari bir olam* [A World of Dreams] // Ma'rifat newspaper. – Tashkent, 4 October 1996.
3. *Education News* [Electronic resource] // Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – Available at: <https://gov.uz/oz/edu/news/view/8957> (accessed: 29 January 2026).
4. *A New Union of Women Scholars: What Will Change in the Future of the Region?* [Electronic resource] // Uzbekistan National News Agency (UZA). – Available at: https://uza.uz/oz/posts/ayol-olimalarning-yangi-ittifoqi-mintaqa-kelajagida-nimalar-ozgaradi-video_789056 (accessed: 29 January 2026).
5. *Women and Men in Uzbekistan: Facts and Figures: Statistical Collection*. – Tashkent: Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2024. – 89 p.

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3. The author's full name should be on the first line from the right; the author's place of work, position, academic degree, and academic rank, email address, and phone number should be on the second line; the article title should be centered in bold, capital letters, on the third line. This information should be provided in Uzbek, English, and Russian.
4. An annotation of 60 words in the next line in three languages.
5. Key words from the next row in three languages 7-10.
6. The next line begins with the main text. The main text begins on the next line, and the article consists of four parts: the relevance of the topic, the methods and level of research, the results, and the conclusion.
7. Articles must be of scientific importance and facts and opinions in the article should be well-grounded and have an independent meaning, and they must be free of plagiarism. The author must clearly demonstrate the literature used in his or her opinion, and provide the exact sources of the extracts.
8. Quotes should be from "Web of science" and "Scopus" journals.
9. A complete list of publications should be followed in alphabetical order after the main text. Seals and references should be in the main text [1, 25].